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DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF ARABIC

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Abstract

More than 450 million people speak Arabic. This language is a language spread over a wide geographical area and is especially important for Muslims. The article examines the stages of development of the Arabic language and its connection with the Qur'an. The Arabic language is important to understand the Holy Quran and the verses in the Quran correctly. Arabic language belongs to the family of Semitic languages. Unlike other Semitic languages, Arabic was a language that reached the highest level. Before the advent of Islam, the Arabic language was divided into two parts: South Arabic and North Arabic. The article mentions that the Arabic language has been preserved thanks to the Holy Quran and has not become a dead language like some languages.

Keywords: Arabic language, Muslim, Holy Quran, Semitic, Islam

The Arabic language has been one of the Semitic languages known to people since ancient times, and it was the language of Ad, Usmud, Wajdis, and Jurhim, and it reached the peak of maturity when it was scattered in Yemen and Iraq and settled in Hijaz. It reached the peak of its glory when it became the language of the Islamic religion. It should be noted that there are approximately 450 million Muslims in the world who speak Arabic.

With the diverse linguistic and cultural origin of Islam, the positive attitude of people in all walks of life and the most remote parts of the world, the presence of the holy book of Islam had a great impact on the enrichment and development of the Arabic language.

Some Arab scholars, such as Mujtahids, Nahivs, and Saraf scholars, have damaged the structure of the Arabic language. Recitation scholars made serious efforts to prevent its degeneration. They gave rise to different recitations of the Qur'an, in the text of the Qur'an

they tried to punctuate correctly. They put forward reasons and evidence as proofs for their claims. Scholars of jurisprudence interpret the verses and sought to obtain a set of necessary rulings and ijthads based on the Shariah in economic, political and religious matters. For this, they aimed to achieve a better appreciation and understanding. Scholars have tried to linguistically develop the rules and regulations that make up Arabic grammar. To accomplish this, they traveled to many different places in the desert. They collected words and tried to develop Arabic grammar by creating competing schools of syntax.

Modern Arabic literary language has been accepted as the official language in Arab countries, whose population together reaches two hundred million. In addition to the literary language, there are local dialects and dialects spoken by the population. Since they are seriously different from each other and also from the literary language, it is considered common that Arabs of different countries do not understand each other, and Arabs without proper training often do not understand

the literary language. The development of the Arabic language consists of several stages. I will analyze these stages in detail in the main part.

Formation of the Arabic language. Islamic scholars and historians have divided all Arab peoples into two large groups:

1. Qahtani, the southern branch that included the ancient Yemeni people (Me'in and Seba'). al-Yemâme, Najd, Hijaz, Shammar and this includes those who live near the border of Arabia with Syria and Iraq.
2. The Ismaili branch, whose center of gravity is in the north, is translated as North Arabic.

The Arabic language has historically gone through three stages of development: ancient (up to the 5th century), classical (5th - 18th century) and modern (from the 19th century to the present) Arabic language. The first written information about the ancient Arabs was found in the inscription of the Assyrian king Sargon (715 BC). The ancient Arabic language was mainly found in Syria, Lihyan, As-Safa, An-Namara, Zabad, Harran, etc. reflected in the inscriptions.

The Quraish (Mecca) dialect played an important role in the formation of the ancient language, which previously consisted of various local dialects, as a literary language in the later stage of development. This language is identified as the first classical Arabic language with a well-established grammatical structure and a rich vocabulary in the examples of oral poetry created immediately before Islam, in the period called Jahiliyyah by Islamic scholars, as well as in the Qur'an, which is considered a very valuable monument.

In the subsequent process of development, the Arabic language is divided into literary languages and dialects that are more and more different from each other. The literary language replaced Aramaic and Greek, which were still used as written languages in the emerging Arab empire, and became the common written language of the empire and is gaining international importance.

The modern Arabic language, which has been developing on the basis of the classical language since the 19th century until today, differs from its predecessor in that the content of the vocabulary is significantly limited due to the removal of archaisms, the creation of words and expressions reflecting new concepts, and the further stabilization of the grammatical structure.

The Arabic language belongs to the Semitic language family, but the origin of the Arabic language is still not fully understood. Let's take a look at the history of the Arabic language. The development of the Arabic language after the establishment of Islam, the development of the Arabic language during the Umayyad and Abbasid periods, the development of the Arabic language during the Mongol invasions, the Arabic language during the Ottoman conquests, the Arabic language at the end of the 9th century, the Arabic language at the end of the 20th century after the Cold War era. Now let's take a closer look and analyze each of these 6 different periods [5, p.4].

Arabic in the post-Islamic period: Arabic became widespread after the Islamic conquests and after the conversion of many peoples, especially the Copts, Assyrians, Syrians, Berbers, and Romans, to Islam. The

spread of the Arabic language during this period, in addition, foreign peoples began to speak Arabic as a second additional language along with their mother tongue, especially during the period of the Umayyad and Abbasid caliphs, Arabic reached its peak of prosperity as it was the language of literature and science, and the Arabic language was the language of rituals that spread during this period. for example, in the Arab world and in the Syrian, Roman, Catholic and Orthodox churches, the Arabic language was widely spread and developed, not to mention that Jews wrote many intellectual and religious works [4].

Arabic language during the Umayyad and Abbasid period: History testifies that the Arabic language spread widely after the Islamic conquests and was at its peak of prosperity, because the language of literature and science was during the Umayyad and Abbasid caliphates and many peoples were influenced by it, for example: Syrians, Romans, Berbers and after the Copts converted to Islam, because the Arabic language was the language of Islamic law and was not worshiped without it, and this led to its widespread use at that time. As many sciences were converted from their own language to Arabic, non-Arabs began to speak it as a second language as well as their mother tongue, and the use of Arabic was not limited to Muslims, but instead became the language used by other religions at that stage, such as Christians in Roman churches and Jews in the Middle Ages. Many religious works were written in Arabic.

The Ajam language played an important role in the development of the Arabic language, especially during the Umayyad and Abbasid periods, and later they translated the sciences into their native languages, which led to the emergence of many new words and terms that did not exist in ancient times. The Qibbi language used to be, for example, the word Bimaristan is a word of Persian origin, and it should be said that the Arabic language reached the golden age of its highest stages of development and progress, especially after the emergence of a large number of scholars, poets, and writers who expressed their beliefs and ideas in Arabic. Many manuscripts and books were written in Arabic. In all cultural and scientific fields and many other foreign languages were also affected during the Crusade period, French, Spanish, English, German and Italian, due to the mixing and amalgamation that occurred between foreigners and Arabs.

Arabic language during the Mongol invasions: During the Mongol invasion led by Hulaku Khan, the Arabic language declined, Islamic civilization and culture were greatly affected by the destruction, and the Arabic language and European civilization began to emerge. The Mongols invaded the Arab world led by the Hulaku leader and during this period the Arabic language experienced its worst state as the Arabic language suffered a great stagnation and lethargy due to great destruction. The Mongol invasion, in its turn, played a major role in the destruction of Arab civilization and culture. Except for this, during the Mamluk era, Arabs did not pay attention to improving and developing science and language before their occupations. By attempting to reform what had been destroyed in the Arab world by Hulaku Khan and his army, the

Spanish reclaimed their country, which led to a significant decline of the Arabic language, especially after the decline and emergence of Arab scientific inventions and discoveries.

Arabic during the Ottoman Conquests: During the Ottoman conquests, the Arabic language was able to establish itself in the Balkans and Anatolia, especially after the conversion of many inhabitants to Islam. During the Ottoman Empire, Arabic became the second official language, as the Ottomans did not have as much interest in culture and science as they had during the Abbasid period. At the end of the Ottoman period, the Arabic language returned to a state of stagnation for nearly four hundred years, and at the end of the 19th century, it recovered a little in Egypt and the Levant, so the number of literate people increased, newspapers and magazines spread, and many writers' associations were created that revived the classical Arabic language. Among the poets and writers of this period are: Ahmed Shawqi, Gibran Khalil Gibran and Nassif Al-Bazji.

Arabic at the end of the ninth century: The Arabic language fell into a state of stagnation for four hundred years, but then recovered somewhat, and this was after the cultural renaissance of the late nineteenth century, especially in Egypt and Damascus. They also started publishing newspapers in Arabic. In addition, many literary societies were created that contributed to the revival of the classical Arabic language. In this period, there are many well-known writers who contributed to the development and enrichment of the Arabic language, including: Sheikh Nasif Al. - Bazaji and Ahmed Showki. He was nicknamed Prince of Poets, Gibran Khalil Gibran and Boutros al-Sabtani. In their hands, modern Arabic dictionaries appeared, for example: the Dictionary of the Department of Knowledge and the Ocean Dictionary, which are still in use, and the Arabic press, which played an important role in the revival of Arabic thought, was born, but it was not limited to the scientific field, but only to literature, and it should be noted that Arabic language no longer plays as big a role in this field, especially after the Cold War Era at the end of the twentieth century, when English became the most common language in the world, be it Arabic or Western, it became the main language used in business messages and deals.

The stages of the historical development and spread of the Arabic language can be shown in a plan as follows: 1. Ancient Arabic language, 2. Classical Arabic language 3. Middle Arabic language 4. New (Modern) Arabic language 5. Constantly developing local dialects [3].

Old Arabic: Examples of Old Arabic can be found in some inscriptions and are known to have existed before 500 AD. Our information about the Old Arabic language and some ancient writings and their relations with the Arabs is based on the corresponding information with individual and tribal names in the texts of the tribes. About the wars between the Assyrians and the Arabs between 626-853 AD, the forty-name document mentioned in the Assyrian Texts is the oldest today. It is known as a written document in Arabic.

Classical Arabic: What is meant by the term Classical Arabic; Its main backbone, which is considered

supra-dialects like the language of science, literature and poetry in the Qur'an and hadith books, ancient literary texts that exist today, as well as in the places where the Arabic language is spread, remains unchanged. This language, which is called classical Arabic, has also marked its progress and development along with the different dialects that existed in different regions before Islam. As for the texts that represent the classical Arabic language, these texts are as follows [2]:

1. Poems of ancient poets (ignorance, muhadramun and the first poets of the Islamic era)
2. The Koran
3. Official correspondence of the Prophet (pbuh) and the first caliphs
4. Hadiths of the Prophet (pbuh).
5. Prose fragments and examples about Eyyamu'l-Arab

Looking at the characteristics of the classical Arabic language, the old scholar investigated which dialect this Arabic was based on. But late scholars have accepted that the basis of this language is the Quraish dialect.

Middle Arabic: The religion of Islam (from the day it was brought to mankind) has a great influence on the development of the Arabic language. The Qur'an has a great influence in determining the basis of the Arabic language. On the other hand, the spread of Islam beyond the borders of the country with the conquests caused the Arabic language to spread to large areas and interact with the languages of the countries it reached. This interaction means a different way of thinking from the Arabs' old ways and a different way of life from theirs (an urban life separated from all aspects of Bedouin life - material and spiritual). This change in lifestyle is effective in feeling and thinking. As it plays a role in language, it naturally undergoes certain changes. In addition, as a result of the translation activities carried out during the Abbasid era, various words were placed in the Arabic language, some of them were Arabized, and the set of words in the Arabic language changed. The language that emerged as a result of this change and interaction is called Middle Arabic.

New (Modern) Arabic language: The printing of Arabic texts began when Napoleon opened a printing press in Egypt. This has been happening since the beginning of the 19th century. As a result of the rapprochement of the Arab world with European culture and civilization, the Arabic language, the language of art, thought and science, is a new (modern) language. It is called in Arabic. In addition, Napoleon's activities such as an observatory, chemical laboratory, theater and library, the opening of many new schools where the teaching methods and programs of European schools were implemented by the governor of Egypt, Kavala Mehmet Ali Pasha, made it necessary to express foreign concepts in Arabic. All these (connections and influences) played an active role in the creation and development of the modern Arabic language [1].

Constantly developing local dialects: On the one hand, old dialects, the language used by Arabs who settled in new places; On the other hand, with different Arabic language, many dialects are spoken under the influence of certain conditions and a dialect was

formed. Each of these is called a local dialect. Literary writing of the Modern Arabic and Middle Arabic period, similar to the language, has also developed rapidly in local dialects. Later, some literary texts increased the ratio between the local dialects and modern Arabic and Middle Arabic. For example, drama, novel, story, etc. For this reason, in some countries where Arabic is used as a spoken language, the idea of replacing local dialects with a common written language has arisen.

The role of the Holy Quran in the development of the Arabic language:

Undoubtedly, one of the most important influences of the Holy Quran on the Arabic language was the unity it provided in the language. He gathered all the Arabs on the Quraish dialect and made the Quraish dialect an important part of the Arabic language. However, before the revelation of the Holy Qur'an, the Arabic language was developing and reaching its peak around the Quraish dialect. However, not all dialects were collected yet. With the revelation of the Holy Quran, the leadership of the Quraysh dialect was completed. With this, the so-called unification attempts, which started from the Jahiliyya period, reached their goal and the language was unified.

The Holy Qur'an has ensured the passage of many previously unknown meanings into the Arabic language and has brought many new words to the Arabic language. The Holy Qur'an was used in the Arabic language and gave the terminological meaning to many existing words, and was the first real factor in the emergence of terminological expressions.

The Arabic language was the language of a certain nation that lived in the Arabian Peninsula before the Quran emerged. It was stuck in the framework of the Arabian Peninsula. The revelation of the Holy Qur'an in the Arabic language made it the language of a heavenly religion and gave it the title of a part of worship. Thus, every Muslim used the Arabic language in his prayers, dhikr, takbir and tashahhud. As a result of the conquests and the growth of the caliphate, along with the conversion of groups of people to Islam, the Arabic language began to spread outside the Arabian Peninsula as far as the Muslims could reach. As a result, the Arabic language continued to spread in parallel with the spread of Islam. Among the languages used in the Islamic world, it rose to the first rank and became the first language.

Languages, like people, are born, live for a certain period of time and then die. However, while saying this,

it is necessary to exclude the Arabic language. Because the Arabic language has become a world language thanks to the Holy Quran and the Holy Quran has protected the Arabic language from all kinds of threats. With the encouragement of Islam, Muslims started memorizing the Quran and reading it all the time. This holy book was the source of life for Muslims. Muslims did not allow even one letter of it to be changed. The protection of the Quran, which is the fortress that protects the Arabic language, by memorization in this way, actually meant the protection of the Arabic language. With the backwardness of the Islamic world, it was feared that the Arabic language, like other languages, would disappear or be influenced by other languages. But thanks to the Holy Quran, the Arabic language has eliminated all worries by protecting itself against all kinds of threats. If it were not for the Quran, the Arabic language was expected to disappear like other languages, or at least to be distorted.

The stages of development of the Arabic language represent the history of the development of the Arab people, as it was one of the dominant Semitic languages in the region during the dominance of the Semitic civilization. Some researchers have classified the stages of the historical development and spread of the Arabic language as Old Arabic, Middle Arabic and New Arabic. From the narratives and poems formed during the Jahiliyyah period to the beginning of the Abbasid era, to the Arabic language, Old Arabic; Middle Arabic, the Arabic language used since the beginning of the Abbasids; The Arabic language used today is New Arabic.

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